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INTRA-ARTICULAR RECONSTRUCTION OF A CRANIAL CRUCIATE LIGAMENT USING AN UHMWPE LIGAMENT IN A CAT: SURGICAL TECHNIQUE DESCRIPTION AND SHORT- AND LONG-TERM OUTCOME

P. Buttin, DVM, DESV ¹, R. Vallefucoco, DVM, DESV, DECVS ²

¹ *VetEchoChir, Villaz, France*

² *Pride Veterinary Referrals, Derby, UK*

Introduction

Cranial cruciate ligament (CrCL) rupture has been successfully managed by intra-articular reconstruction using an ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) implant fixed by femoral and tibial titanium interference screws in dogs. However, due to the smaller size of cat' stifle, smaller implants and adaptation of the intra-articular reconstruction technique are needed. Here, we describe the technique used to reconstruct the CrCL in a cat, and we report the short- and long- term clinical outcome.

Methods

A 5-kg European cat was diagnosed with a complete rupture of the CrCL associated with a grade 2/4 lameness. No muscular atrophy nor meniscal lesion were observed. Both direct and indirect drawer tests were positive. The intra-articular reconstruction of the CrCL was achieved using a UHMWPE synthetic ligament, anchored to the medial aspect of the tibia by a cortical button and through a femoral tunnel by a 3-mm titanium interference screw.

Results

Clinical and radiographic assessment showed a restoration of the normal function of the operated stifle and the return to a normal physical activity. At 8 months, the cat had a normal gait, no pain, and a normal range of motion. The stifle was stable with absence of pivot shift or direct and indirect translation. Overall, the clinical outcome was satisfactory.

Conclusions

This intra-articular synthetic reconstruction of the CrCL resulted in a good clinical outcome with no complications in this case. This supports the suitability of this technique in similar cases.

Corresponding Address

Dr. Philippe Buttin - VetEchoChir, 471 Chemin de Ronzier, 74370 VILLAZ, FRANCE -

E-mail philippebuttin@gmail.com